

ADVANTAGES OF REGULAR ASSESSMENT AND FEEDBACK OF THE MANAGEMENT COMPETENCE OF DIRECTORS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

*The article comprehensively discusses the benefits of
regular assessment and feedback of the managerial
competence of directors of preschool educational
organizations..*

Increasing managerial efficiency: the information received helps the director to timely correct managerial decisions and increase work efficiency.

Development of professional competencies: regular assessment encourages the director to continuous professional and personal growth, as well as to develop skills in solving complex managerial problems.

Improving the quality of the educational process: based on the feedback received, changes and improvements can be made to improve the quality of education and the satisfaction of all participants in the educational process.

Thus, regular assessment of activities and collection of feedback are an indispensable tool for effective management of a preschool educational organization, contributing to the continuous improvement and development of the organization and its leader.

The pedagogical conditions created for the development of the director's managerial competencies in a preschool educational organization should contribute not only to improving managerial competencies, but also to creating an environment in which each employee participates in the process of improving the quality of education. Creating such conditions requires a comprehensive approach, including changes in educational policy, as well as corporate culture and methods of working with employees.

For the effective development of the managerial competence of the director of preschool educational organizations, it is necessary to create pedagogical conditions that will help not only increase managerial competencies, but also form an inclusive, involved and innovative educational environment. This requires a comprehensive approach that includes changes in educational policy, corporate culture and employee relations.

An integrated approach to creating pedagogical conditions in a preschool educational organization includes the following aspects:

1. Changes in educational policy:

Development and implementation of standards and requirements for the managerial competencies of directors, which will help consolidate and increase managerial competencies in preschool educational organizations.

Support for innovative educational programs and projects aimed at improving the quality of education and developing the managerial skills of directors.

Reform the regulatory framework governing the activities of preschool educational organizations to ensure greater autonomy and flexibility in managing educational processes.

2. Changes in corporate culture:

Creating a culture of openness and mutual respect, in which each employee feels like a valuable part of the team and can freely express their ideas and suggestions.

Encouraging initiative and creativity in employees, which will contribute to their personal and professional growth.

Developing mentoring and coaching programs that will help new and less experienced directors adapt faster and successfully manage the organization.

3. Methods of working with employees:

Regular training and advanced training of all employees of preschool educational organizations to maintain a high level of professionalism and update knowledge of modern pedagogical and managerial practices.

Introducing a feedback and performance evaluation system that will allow directors and employees to receive constructive criticism and suggestions for improving their work.

Create motivational mechanisms to encourage high performance, including rewards, awards, and public recognition of achievements.

The use of these approaches creates favorable conditions for the development of managerial competencies of directors of preschool educational organizations, which in turn has a positive effect on the quality of preschool education, making the educational process more efficient and responsive to modern requirements.

For an effective model of developing the managerial competencies of the director of a preschool educational organization, it is necessary to create specific pedagogical conditions that ensure his professional growth and increase the overall quality of management of the organization. The main pedagogical conditions that should be considered here are:

1. Vocational education and training: providing opportunities for continuing education and professional development, including specialized courses in the management of educational organizations, management, innovative educational technologies and teaching methods.

2. Mentoring and coaching: Develop a mentoring system where experienced directors or external experts can provide guidance, support and feedback to early childhood education directors, helping them in their professional and personal growth.

3. Collaborative environment: Create a structure that encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing between directors of different preschool educational organizations to discuss successful practices, challenges and decisions, which will help improve management skills.

4. Innovative learning environment: Introduce modern educational technologies and encourage an innovative approach to teaching and learning so that directors can experiment and implement new methods and tools of management and teaching.

5. Feedback and Evaluation: Develop a systematic and systematic system for collecting and analyzing feedback from educators, parents, and children, which will help directors identify areas for improvement and monitor the effectiveness of the changes made.

6. Ethical and Cultural Standards: Foster and support strong ethical and cultural standards in management, ensuring respect, fairness, and transparency in all aspects of Dow's work.

7. Resource Support: Ensure adequate resources, including funds, equipment, and materials, to implement educational and management initiatives.

Creating such pedagogical conditions will help directors of preschool educational organizations not only develop their own managerial and pedagogical skills, but also effectively manage the organization, ensuring high quality of the educational process.

Creating adequate pedagogical conditions is important for the development of managerial and pedagogical skills of directors of preschool educational organizations. The importance of these conditions is that they not only ensure the professional training and development of principals, but also help create an effective management structure that directly affects the quality of the educational process.

1. Professional education and training provide directors with the opportunity to receive continuous education through specialized courses and programs. This includes learning about best management practices, management and the latest educational technologies and teaching methods.

2. Mentoring and coaching help directors grow professionally and personally. Experienced directors or external experts can offer the necessary support and feedback, which is a valuable resource for developing management skills and solving everyday problems.

3. A collaborative environment creates conditions for the exchange of knowledge and experience between directors of different organizations. Discussion of successful practices and ongoing problems helps to improve managerial competencies and make effective managerial decisions.

4. An innovative learning environment encourages directors to experiment with new approaches and technologies. The introduction of innovative methods of management and teaching helps to develop the learning process and makes it more attractive and effective for children.

5. Feedback and evaluation allow directors to understand which aspects of the organization's work require improvement. Regular collection and analysis of feedback from educators, parents, and children helps to identify successful strategies and shortcomings in the organization's activities.

6. Ethical and cultural standards ensure the creation of fair and transparent management practices, which is important for maintaining trust and a high level of professionalism in the organization.

7. Resource support, including sufficient funding, necessary equipment, and materials, is essential for the implementation of educational and management initiatives.

The implementation of these conditions will allow directors of preschool educational organizations not only to develop their own managerial and pedagogical skills, but also to effectively manage the organization, ensuring the high quality of the educational process.

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